

Navigating the Digital Era with Emotional Intelligence

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ABSTRACT

In today's digital era, the pervasive integration of Technology into daily life has raised questions about its influence on fundamental aspects of human behaviour and cognition. In addition to making the academic content easier to access and enhancing academic abilities, technology is increasingly recognized for its potential to support students in developing their emotional intelligence (EI). **Emotional intelligence**, often referred to as **EQ**, encompasses the ability to recognize, understand, and manage one's own emotions, as well as the emotions of others. This paper aims to investigate the relationship between Technology use and **Emotional Intelligence (EI)**, a crucial component of human social and emotional functioning. Through a comprehensive review of existing literature, Technology can provide opportunities for enhancing certain aspects of emotional intelligence, such as Empathy and social awareness; it also presents challenges that may impede its development. The study offers a thorough grasp of the ways in which Technology may affect people's emotional growth, expression, and regulation.

Keywords: Education, Technology, Emotional Intelligence, Social Media, Virtual Reality, Artificial Intelligence.

1. INTRODUCTION

Given the technological dominance of today's society, emotional intelligence (EI) is crucial. While there is no denying that technological advancements have significantly benefited society, they have also altered interpersonal interactions and communication. In this setting, effective leadership, productive teamwork, and general satisfaction with the job all depend heavily on emotional intelligence (**Zahyd S, 2023**). In recent years, the pervasive integration of Technology into various aspects of human life has raised concerns about its impact on social and emotional well-being. The development of digital Technology has had a significant on human life in this era of rapid technological advancement. Children's use of digital devices has significantly increased (**Nu rAzimah et al., 2021**). There are concerns over the possible impact of children's Technology use on their emotions and psyche due to the difficulties that arise from it. **Giusi Antonia Toto and PierpaoloLimone's** new study from **2021** has sparked worries about how Technology affects kids' emotional and psychological growth.

This study formed the assumption that aspects of emotional intelligence would affect an individual's sense of self-efficacy, making emotional intelligence an essential factor in the

field of Technology adoption. In this proposed framework linked relational models of emotional intelligence features to theories of technology adoption (**Abu-Shanab, E. A., & Shanab, A. A., 2022**). Studies indicated a connection between DM and EI. Individuals with brain harm struggle with social and emotional problems in their relationships with others, which affects their decision-making. An argument like this indicates how emotional behaviour and cognitive skills interact to influence an individual's ability to make wise decisions or decisions that are acceptable to their surroundings. However, one of the biggest challenges to employing Technology for DM is Technology adoption. Studies have indicated that adopting of Technology is significantly influenced by personality factors (**Abu-Shanab and Pearson, 2007**).

The increasing integration of Technology into the lives of both adults and children makes it imperative to ascertain how it impacts the psychological processes that underlie human behaviour in general. More specifically, there are worries about how Technology may affect kids' social and emotional development when introduced into the family environment (**Radesky & Christakis, 2016**). A comprehensive understanding of the interplay between Technology and human development would require a thorough investigation of the various facets that remain to be explored (**Edwards et al., 2017; O'Connor & Fotakopoulou, 2016**).

Many smart device apps promote daily or even hourly use, which begs the question of how this usage impacts day-to-day living in general (Milijic, 2019). Thus, scholars tried to examine the connections between various behaviours and smart device use, such as sleep (**Demirci, Akgönül, & Akpınar, 2015**), stress (**Samaha & Hawai, 2016**), depression (**Alhassan et al., 2018**), self-esteem (**Işiklar, şar, & Durmuşcelebi, 2013**), and anxiety (**Elhai, Levine, Dvorak, & Hall, 2016**). Studies on the impact of Technology on the social and emotional development of teenagers (**Lee & Lee, 2017**) and school-age children (**Hale & Guan, 2015**) have been conducted. However, when researching younger children, the focus is frequently on the parent's use rather than the child's (**McDaniel & Radesky, 2018**).

According to **Daniel Goleman (2013)**, Emotional Intelligence is more significant than cognitive ability in predicting an individual's performance and achievement in life, which means that Emotional Intelligence plays an important part in an individual's success and well-being. He asserts that a person's success, particularly in learning, is significantly influenced by their level of Emotional Intelligence. According to **Goleman's (1995)** book Emotional Intelligence, an individual's **20% academic intelligence** and **80% skill at efficiently** controlling their emotions determine their level of brilliance. In a study of EI clearly shows that having a high level of "emotional management" in one's life is highly valued by successful people (**Zainuddin, 2000**).

Nurul Aini & Siti Marziah (2018) say that positive emotional development predicts future success in relationships, health, and overall quality of life. Once more, he asserts that kids with strong emotional intelligence get good grades, attend school longer, and generally make better decisions. Their emotional intelligence can significantly influence a person's level of motivation because of their capacity to control their thoughts, feelings, and mental faculties in specific contexts. As per **Colomeischi & Colomeishi (2014)**, the correlation among

emotional intelligence, self-efficacy, and activity fulfilment shapes the worth and execution of that particular activity, hence refining children's abilities and aptitudes towards their inclinations. As a result, we need to focus enough on enhancing and growing emotional intelligence during the formative years of childhood.

Objectives

- To discuss Technology and Emotional intelligence.
- To discuss the role of Technology in the development of Emotional Intelligence.
- To explore strategies for enhancing Emotional Intelligence in the Digital Age.
- To investigate data on the utilization and perception of Technology for Emotional Intelligence Development across various countries.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The number of studies looking at how Technology affects people's mental health has increased recently. **Shek and Yu** warned that Internet addiction is a growing problem globally, particularly among teenagers, in light of the rapidly increasing number of people using the Internet. **According to Milford et al.**, students get used to using a variety of social media platforms (such as blogs, social networks, and forums) for various objectives, including communication, learning, and entertainment. **According to Young**, four elements influence students' use of social media: apps, emotions, cognition, and life events. Emotions have the strongest connections to emotional intelligence of the four abovementioned characteristics. The ability to identify and comprehend one's own emotions as well as interpersonal skills is components of emotional intelligence.

A significant majority of students in **North America** assert that they prefer digital learning methods over traditional ones, as seen by the statistic "**Over 70% of students say they prefer learning digitally.**" According to the data, 30% of **K–12 educators** think that by **2021**, artificial intelligence will be more widely used in the classroom. According to the statistic, "**48%** of students report using **online tutoring services** to enhance their learning," almost half of the student body surveyed said they had used online tutoring as a way to augment their academic experience ¹(**Jannik**).

Mobile phones are the most ubiquitous piece of hardware found in schools worldwide, despite their frequent classroom absence. Several educational authorities have officially outlawed cell phones in classrooms, even though **62% of people worldwide** own a mobile phone (**Statista, 2021**)². These authorities include the Ministries of Education in **China** and **France**, as well as the provinces, states, and schools in **Canada, Australia, the US, and the UK (Wakefield, 2021)**³. In **Latin America**, the former Eastern Bloc, and English-speaking European nations, the rate of loneliness has approximately doubled since **2012**; in East Asian nations, it has climbed by **50%** (**Twenge et al., 2021**). Several experimental studies of global Sesame Street variations conducted in **Bangladesh, Egypt, Indonesia, Tanzania, South Africa, and Tanzania** have demonstrated that exposure to Sesame Street can lead to positive

¹<https://wifitalents.com/statistic/technology-in-education/>

²<https://www.statista.com/>

³<https://wifitalents.com/statistic/technology-in-education/>

outcomes on gender-equitable attitudes, literacy, numeracy, and **social and emotional development** in addition to better school readiness (**Borzekowski, 2018; Borzekowski and Macha, 2010; Watson, 2019**). Universities use AI to understand self-regulated learning better in **the US, Australia, New Zealand, Germany, France, and the Netherlands**. Examples include using lecture transcript analysis to support reflective teaching practices, leveraging machine learning techniques to better understand self-regulated learning, creating personalized scaffolds to support students' meta-cognitive skills, and helping university students develop AI competencies (**According to Pelletier et al., 2021**).

A game, an evaluation, and weekly videos with stories and narratives were all part of a **game-based social and emotional learning program** for **third-grade students** in the **US state of California**. As a result, the student's interpersonal communication and skills—including **empathy** and **Emotional Regulation**—improved compared to the control group (**Sanchez et al., 2017**). **According to the Singapore Ministry of Education, 2022, The 2019 Education Technology plan encouraged** digital Technology and individualised, self-directed learning. Considering the increased exposure to digital spaces, emotional competencies were given additional room in the most recent curriculum revision. A comprehensive examination of a sizable cohort of youth in the **United States**, ages 2 to 17, revealed a negative correlation between increased **screen time and worse levels of emotional stability, curiosity, self-control, and anxiety**, as well as more significant diagnoses of depression and Some of these associations were stronger for teenagers than for younger children (**Twenge and Campbell, 2018**). Although AI Technology is developing quickly, the skills required of people in the field have not changed much in the last ten years. Along with cognitive talents, working with AI requires a great deal of emotional intelligence in communication, creativity, and teamwork (**Samek et al., 2021**).⁴

3. TECHNOLOGY

The World Bank Group, which works on education projects in more than **80 countries** to provide high-quality education and chances for lifelong learning for everyone, is the biggest donor to education in developing nations. As part of its wider work related to education, the **WBG** collaborates with governments and organizations worldwide to support creative projects, timely research, and knowledge-sharing activities about the appropriate and effective use of information and communication technologies (ICTs) in education systems -- "**EdTech**" -- to improve learning and contribute to poverty reduction worldwide. **The World Bank** estimated the percentage of **10-year-old children** who, by the end of primary school, cannot read and comprehend a short story to determine the extent of "**Learning Poverty**" worldwide. The percentage of people "**learning poverty**" in low- and middle-income nations is **53%**; in the world's poorest nations, the **average is 80%**. Around **180 nations** implemented temporary school closures because of the **COVID-19 pandemic**, which

⁴https://digitallibrary.in.one.un.org/TempPdfFiles/8207_1.pdf

affected almost **85%** of children globally and resulted in the absence of education for approximately **1.6 billion children** and youth at its peak. **(The World Bank Report)⁵**

Over the past 20 years, educators, students, and institutions have made extensive use of digital technological tools. From **0 in 2012** to at least **220 million** in **2021**, more students were enrolled in **MOOCs** (massive open online courses). In **2023**, there were **20 million active users** of the language-learning software **Duolingo**, while in **2021**, **Wikipedia** had **244 million daily page views**. **According to the 2018 PISA**, **54%** of schools with an efficient online learning support platform available had 15-year-old students, and **65%** of students in **OECD countries** were in schools where principals agreed that teachers had the technical and pedagogical skills to integrate digital devices into instruction. These shares are thought to have increased during the **COVID-19 pandemic**. The proportion of people using the Internet increased globally from **16% in 2005** to **66% in 2022**. In **2022**, approximately half of the world's lower secondary schools had an Internet connection for educational purposes. **(The Global Education Monitoring Report, 2023)⁶**

4. EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE

Emotional intelligence, often known as social intelligence, was listed as one of the main traits of humans in the many intelligences theory put forth by **Gardner (1983)** and **Gardner and Hatch (1989)**. **According to Mayer et al. (2008), p. 508**, emotion is "the integrated feeling experience involving physiological changes, motor-preparedness, and cognitions about action, and inner experiences that emerge from an appraisal of the self or situation."

In the theory of multiple intelligences, **Howard Gardner (1983)** suggested the concept of social intelligence, which is an extension of the ever-evolving idea of emotional intelligence. A person's capacity to identify, comprehend, and utilize language in social contexts to communicate their own and other people's feelings is referred to as emotional intelligence. In short, emotional intelligence can be proposed in four significant dimensions - understanding one's own emotions, managing one's own emotions, understanding the emotions of others, and managing the emotions of others.

Salovey and Mayer (1990) defined **emotional intelligence (EI)** as the subclass of social intelligence that encompasses the ability to regulate one's own emotions as well as those of others. This intelligence regulates emotion to direct one's thoughts and behaviours **(Chrusciel, 2006)**.

It is generally accepted that social intelligence includes emotional intelligence as a subset. The ability to manage one's own emotions, assess the feelings of others, differentiate between emotions, and utilize this knowledge to inform one's decisions and behaviour are all components of emotional intelligence. **Goleman** defines emotional intelligence as the ability to recognize one's own feelings as well as those of others, control one's own emotions in social situations, and, when required, inspire oneself. **According to Bar-On**, emotional intelligence is a collection of non-cognitive skills and aptitudes that influence how well a

⁵<https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/edutech>

⁶<https://gem-report-2023.unesco.org/technology-in-education/>Global education monitoring report, 2023: technology in education: a tool on whose terms? UNESCO Digital Library.

person reacts to demands made of them by their surroundings. In terms of human traits, emotional intelligence, **according to Petrides and Furnham**, is a synthesis of traits like emotionality, self-control, sociality, and well-being. The definition of emotional intelligence has been the subject of considerable discussion among these and other researchers, but **Salovey and Mayer** are the forerunners in this field. They defined emotional intelligence as consisting of four components: the ability to perceive emotion, the ability to use emotion to aid in thought, the ability to understand emotion, and the ability to manage emotion. Maintaining emotional self-control is crucial. According to a meta-analysis, academic achievement is well predicted by one's capacity for emotional understanding and regulation (**MacCann et al., 2020**). A comprehensive analysis discovered that when predicting academic achievement, some social and emotional traits—most notably self-regulation—were more important than IQ (**Costa, 2019**).

5. TECHNOLOGY AND EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE

Technology's effects extend beyond psychology; they can also be felt from an emotional perspective. This is clear when seen from the perspective of peer and child-parent communication. The framework for understanding the impact of Technology on emotional intelligence draws from theories of emotional development, cognitive psychology, and human-computer interaction. Emotional development theories emphasize the role of social interactions and environmental influences in shaping emotional competencies from infancy through adulthood. Cognitive psychology provides insights into the cognitive processes underlying emotional intelligence, such as perception, attention, memory, and decision-making. Human-computer interaction theories offer perspectives on how individuals interact with and adapt to Technology-mediated environments **Hashim, N., & Razali, A. (2019)**.

Judy Brown, Denise L. Winsor, and Sally Blake talk about the research on the relationship between Technology and emotional development, how parents view social interactions in the context of children and adults, the theoretical influences on learning environments, and strategies for using tools to support these crucial domains globally. Early childhood educators need to change how they support their students socially and emotionally because technology has changed the socio-cultural landscape globally. (**Judy Brown, Denise L. Winsor & Sally Blake, 2012**)

6. NAVIGATING THE DIGITAL ERA WITH EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE

As we navigate the complexities of the digital age, cultivating emotional intelligence becomes increasingly important. Here are some strategies for harnessing Technology to enhance our emotional intelligence:

- 6.1 Practice Digital Mindfulness:** Be mindful of your digital habits and how they impact your emotions and well-being. Set boundaries around Technology use, take regular breaks, and engage in activities that promote relaxation and self-reflection.
- 6.2 Foster Face-to-Face Connections:** While digital communication has its place, prioritize face-to-face interactions whenever possible. Invest time building and nurturing meaningful relationships with friends, family, and colleagues.

6.3 Use Technology as a Tool for Growth: Embrace Technology for personal and professional growth. Seek digital resources, such as online courses, podcasts, and self-help apps, that support your emotional development and well-being.

6.4 Practice Empathy in the Digital World: Be mindful of the impact of online interactions on others. Practice Empathy and kindness in your digital communications, and seek to understand different perspectives and experiences.

6.5 Balance Technology Use with Offline Activities: Find a balance between online and offline activities. Make time for hobbies, interests, and activities that nourish your emotional well-being and foster connection with others.

7. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the relationship between Technology and Emotional Intelligence is multifaceted, with positive and negative implications. To maximize technology's potential advantages while minimizing its disadvantages, it is essential to adopt a balanced approach that promotes mindful and purposeful Technology use. Future research should continue to explore the dynamic interplay between Technology and emotional intelligence across different contexts and populations, emphasizing fostering socio-emotional well-being in the digital age. By understanding and addressing the complex interactions between Technology and emotional intelligence, we can strive towards a future where Technology enhances rather than diminishes our capacity for empathic and emotionally intelligent behaviour.

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